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PROSPECTIVE WAYS OF DEVELOPMENT OF MILITARY MANAGEMENT

Tulyaganova Shokhiya Gaffurovna

Ph.D. in Economics, associate professor,
Academy of the Armed Forces of the Republic of Uzbekistan

Abstract: This article explores the evolution of military management and its fundamental principles during the second stage, spanning from the first quarter of the 18th century to the end of the 19th century.

Key words: principles, functions, military leader, commander, management, military management, manager, military manager, managerial qualities of a military manager.

INTRODUCTION

Personnel management is one of the most important aspects of any institution's operations, as employees significantly enhance its efficiency. Management, as a result of labor division, has existed for millennia, dating back to the emergence of civilization, when organizations became a phenomenon of social life. However, while management practices have always existed, the discipline itself was formally established as a scientific field in the late 19th – early 20th centuries [1].

Throughout history, one of the key factors in stabilizing or disrupting military management systems has been the relationship and rational balance between politics and military strategy. For nearly 200 years, it has been widely accepted that war is a continuation of politics—essentially a violent extension of policy. Consequently, politics represents the whole, while war is a component of management that shapes the political climate and maintains dominance over military strategy. This underscores humanity's long-standing recognition of management as a distinct activity. However, as a branch of knowledge, management began to take shape in the second half of the 18th century, with its full development occurring in the early 20th century during the industrialization era and the emergence of large-scale organizations in terms of resource consumption and operational scope.

Before discussing the manager and their functions, it is necessary to define the concept of "management" itself. The term originates from the American word "management," derived from "to manage" [1]. However, a universally accepted scientific definition of management has not yet been established. This is because management applies to various fields, including commercial and non-commercial enterprises, economic activities, and the social sphere. Different classifications of management exist, such as technological, strategic, innovative, and military management, among others, leading to the broad scope of management science [2].

Management is a unique type of human relationship in which one individual seeks to achieve an outcome from another that the latter would not accomplish independently. As a result, "management" remains one of the most ambiguous and broadly defined categories. We manage airplanes, our free time, teams, and more. The theory of management is an ancient discipline, predating the works of 19th-century American engineers and originating from ancient philosophers who discussed the art of governing people in politics, trade, military operations, and diplomacy. Management must have its own theoretical foundation, as neither the experience of a single manager nor that of an entire management team can account for the vast diversity of management situations.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Michael Mescon believes¹ that management is the process of planning, organizing, motivating, and controlling, which are necessary to formulate and achieve an organization's goals through other people.

The development of management practices and the emergence of management as a field of knowledge date back to the very beginning of human existence. From the earliest times, human labor was conscious and, to some extent, organized. Daily activities required coordination among community members, as well as the subordination of some individuals to the will of others. With the advancement of civilizations, management processes became more complex, incorporating elements of foresight and calculations. Those who mastered these skills rose to positions of influence, becoming priests, pharaohs, and ministers figures who embodied wisdom, power, and wealth in their states.

¹ Meskon M.Kh. Fundamentals of Management: trans. from English / M.Kh. Meskon, M. Albert, F. Kheldouri. – M.: Delo, 1992.

Management has existed in human society since time immemorial. Even in primitive societies, it was necessary to organize, plan, and control activities such as food gathering, storage, shelter construction, tribal protection, and the transmission of knowledge, skills, traditions, and customs. These functions were performed by specific groups of people leaders, elders, military commanders, and priests. Over time, management processes became more structured and specialized, involving large groups of people dedicated to governing the state and the army [8].

Socrates, analyzing the activities of managers across different fields, identified a common principle underlying their work [3]: the primary task of management is to place the right person in the right position and ensure that their instructions are effectively carried out.

The Italian statesman Niccolò Machiavelli made a significant contribution to the development of management thought. In particular, he stated: “Many believe that some sovereigns who are reputed to be wise owe their glory not to themselves but to the good advice of their confidants. However, this opinion is erroneous. For the rule that knows no exception is this: it is useless to give good advice to a sovereign who does not himself possess wisdom” [4].

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This article examines the scientific and theoretical foundations of the evolution, origin, and development of military management in developed states. The study employs methods such as verbal explanation, statistical observation, induction and deduction, and scientific abstraction.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

The history of civilization provides numerous examples of various management styles; however, humanity quickly forgets these lessons. The triumphant expansion of the Roman Empire’s legions was the result of a well-structured army management system, where iron discipline was maintained at every level—century, cohort, and legion. Clear goals and structured methods for solving specific problems were established. Similarly, the straightforward and well-defined structure of the Roman Catholic Church, established by the founders of Christianity, has ensured its continued functioning with minimal changes to this day.

However, the management structures and organizational foundations of antiquity differ significantly from those of the modern era. This distinction is clearly illustrated in *Table 1*, which has been referenced from the work [2].

Table 1. Comparison of old and new management organization.

Old organization	Modern organization
Few large organizations, no giant organizations	A large number of extremely powerful large organizations, both commercial and non-profit
Relatively small number of managers, virtual absence of middle managers	A large number of managers, a large number of middle managers
Management work was often not distinguished or separated from non-managerial activities.	Management groups are clearly defined, management work is separated from non-managerial activities
Occupation of leadership positions in an organization is most often by birthright or by force of seizure	Taking up leadership positions in an organization is most often done by right of competence in compliance with the law
Few people capable of making important decisions for the organization	A large number of people capable of making important decisions for the organization
Emphasis on command and intuition	Emphasis on teamwork

Management emerged as an independent field of human knowledge a science only at the end of the 19th century. During this period, multi-million-man armies appeared, making their management increasingly complex. Consequently, there was an urgent need to develop both the theory and practice of managing such vast military forces. The decisive role in addressing the challenges of military management was played by Russia’s advanced military thought, developed by prominent theorists such as P.I. Pestel, N.V. Medem, D.A. Milyutin, F.I. Goremykin, A.I. Astafyev, G.A. Leer, M.I. Dragomirov, A.N. Petrov, and others. Analyzing their scientific works on military management allows us to derive substantiated principles of military leadership. In naming these principles, we will use modern management terminology.

Pavel Ivanovich Pestel (1793–1826), summarizing the experience of the Patriotic War of 1812, identified two levels of military management:

“Military government is divided into the supreme government and subordinate governments. Subordinate governments are divided into the Administrative Order and the Executive Order” [5]. Russian military theory and practice, as exemplified by renowned commanders such as A.V. Suvorov and M.I. Kutuzov, also made significant contributions to the development of military management. Suvorov’s success in over 50 years of campaigns and wars (1750–1800) was largely due to his application of not only fundamental principles of tactics, training, and troop education but also advanced and revolutionary military management strategies.

The principles of Suvorov’s military management were later utilized by Russian commanders during the Patriotic War of 1812, as well as by Soviet military leaders in the Great Patriotic War (1941–1945) and World War II (1939–1945). These principles played a crucial role in the defeat of Napoleon in 1812, as well as Hitler and the Japanese forces in 1945. Remarkably, Suvorov’s military management principles remain relevant today and continue to be applied in modern military strategies [7].

The thinkers of Ancient Greece made a significant contribution to the development of management science. Socrates (469–399 BC), emphasizing the importance of the division of labor and specialization, viewed the tasks of management as ensuring that each person was in the right place. He and other ancient Greek philosophers argued that the root cause of poverty in society was, in most cases, the lack of skillful distribution of labor. History provides many examples illustrating the development of management. One of the enduring guidelines, *instruction*, remains relevant to this day: “If you are a boss, be calm when you listen to the words of a petitioner; do not push him away before he has relieved his soul of what he wanted to tell you. A person struck by misfortune wants to pour out his soul even more than he desires a favorable solution to his problem.”

At each stage of management development, Pestel substantiated the relevant bodies and their structures, as well as the procedures for selecting and appointing military personnel. He asserted: “Experience or appointment from one position to a more important one should be based on abilities and distinction, not on seniority, for the service is not established for the benefit of commanders (chiefs), but rather, commanders (chiefs) are determined for the benefit of the service.” [5]

Medem Nikolai Vasilyevich (1790–1870), in his scientific study *Tactics*, concluded: “Victory with an equal number of active troops depends primarily on their structure and quality, as well as on the art of their commanders or managers. However, in addition to these conditions, each army must possess two other essential qualities: discipline and moral strength, without which the first conditions will not yield the desired benefit.” [5]

Milyutin Dmitry Alekseevich (1812–1912) proposed the most modern structure for the army, including corps, divisions, and regiments, as well as an effective management system for them [4]. He emphasized the necessity of decentralization and initiative in military management, advocating for the removal of unnecessary military personnel from the headquarters of commanders-in-chief. Additionally, he analyzed the evolving role of human resources and technology in future wars.

Fyodor Ivanovich Goremykin (1813-1850), in his fundamental work “Guide to the Study of Tactics” (1849), developed the theory of military management. He defined the place and role of tactics within the framework of other military sciences, substantiated the structure of troops, and outlined the necessary qualities of troops in both material and moral aspects. He wrote: “Moral conditions include adaptation to a military goal, which many writers now call moral strength, but in language more understandable to soldiers, it is expressed in one word: military spirit. In this state, regardless of the greater or lesser belligerence of their natural character, all people belonging to one army must be brought; it binds everyone into one harmonious whole, driven by one thought and capable of the same efforts” [5].

Alexander Ivanovich Astafyev (1816 – after 1863) further developed the theory of military management in his scientific work “On Modern Military Art” [5.]. In this work, he substantiated the organizational structure of the army, the components of military management as a science, the requirements for military managers, the role and place of the military manager in administration, and other related aspects.

The main provisions of his work are as follows:

The army is the primary means by which the objective of war is achieved. The success of war depends on intelligence and strength. These two components are essential for achieving the goal of war and must be united, like the soul and the body. Intelligence without strength, as well as strength without intelligence, means nothing. The moral and physical elements undoubtedly exist within the army. There is an assumption that the moral principle resides in the commander, as its head, while the material aspect is more inherent in the army itself, as its organism, carrying out the will of its leader.

The goal of war is to destroy the enemy, but in order to accomplish this, it is necessary to perfect military management by understanding:

- a) the one who is acting;
- b) the means with which he is acting;

- c) the target he is destroying;
- d) the best course of action leading to success.

If we seek to achieve success, it is essential that both the commander (chief) and the army (military unit) strive for perfection towards the ideal.

Requirements for a commander (military leader). A commander must not be mediocre; if not a comprehensive genius, they should at least possess a universal education and a truly healthy and practical outlook on matters.

To effectively lead an army and master the art of war, it is essential to have a thorough understanding of the properties and qualities of all military branches. Additionally, if possible, a commander should progress through all ranks to personally experience the life of every soldier under their command. This is why all great military leaders did not disdain lower positions but instead began their service as ordinary soldiers. For instance, Peter the Great served in a regiment as a drummer and quartermaster, passing through all ranks. Frederick the Great mingled with soldiers, conversed with them, and even shared snuff from the same snuffbox. Napoleon was affectionately called the "Little Corporal" by his troops. Suvorov, not hesitating to sit with soldiers at the communal pot, studied their spirit and way of life, making them willing instruments of his thoughts and will this being the primary reason for his immense success [7].

A commander's knowledge of his most crucial weapon the army and the ability to wield it effectively represent the highest level of military leadership. This mastery is achieved by practically studying a soldier's life, as they form the core of the military structure. From the above, it follows that a leader must possess a perfect understanding of military strategy and governance. This means having the ability to harness both the physical and spiritual strength of troops to secure victory in war.

4. Military leadership at every level. Every commander and every unit, no matter how small, represents the army in a microcosm. Therefore, the universal education, principles, and moral (spiritual) qualities expected of the commander-in-chief should also be cultivated in each military officer, proportionate to the size and purpose of the unit they command. In other words, every element of the army must be trained in alignment with the objectives set by its leadership.

5. Strategic principles at all levels. Strategic principles apply not only to large-scale operations but also to small detachments and even individual soldiers. The fundamental strategic thought expressed through intelligence and cunning remains the same regardless of scale. Maneuvers such as feints, ambushes, rear attacks, and flanking movements are tactics used at all levels of command. The key difference lies in the varying circumstances surrounding each scenario, though the core strategic concept remains consistent for every soldier and leader alike.

6. Knowledge of higher sciences that do not correspond to one's position will be, at most, a temporary curiosity; however, curiosity is in no way worthy of censure. Every military man who chooses to study an advanced field, having first mastered what pertains to his duties, may, out of curiosity, explore the higher aspects of military art, the principles of which should be learned in advance. Everyone should strive for an education that aligns with their sphere of activity, position, and purpose.

7. Each officer must have an understanding of all branches of the military and be, to some extent, an infantryman, sapper, artilleryman, etc. In other words, an officer's education must be universal, as they are responsible for implementing the commander's directives and conveying them to the army. Officers must be regarded as individuals from whom future military leaders can be developed.

8. Waging war requires: recruiting, equipping, and arming personnel assigned to military service; forming them into a unified, well-organized force (army) that is manageable and effective in combat; administering and maintaining the army in an orderly and disciplined manner.

9. The moral authority of a military leader his ideas, orders, and interactions with the army, as well as his relations with external entities and circumstances is fully reflected in the role of those who serve as intermediaries between the leader and the troops.

10. Order necessitates harmony, which depends on the division of the army into both larger and smaller units. To achieve this, each unit must be assigned a commanding officer who embodies its essence and possesses the authority appropriate to its size. Each must have clearly defined responsibilities, areas of operation, and interactions with the troops under his command. In essence, the army must be governed by structured regulations and an organization designed to fulfill its purpose effectively.

11. Military operations take place in both peacetime and wartime. In peacetime, they involve public works, security duties, training camps, large-scale maneuvers, garrison services, and other preparatory activities. In wartime, military operations consist of combat engagements. Officers, as the primary assistants and executors of the commander's will, must ensure that all actions align with the fulfillment of his objectives. From this, we can conclude that military education must be comprehensive and universal.

12. In administrative and combat-related written orders, the military requires a specialized language one that is aligned with the principles and spirit of the armed forces. This language must be clear, concise, and precise,

avoiding unnecessarily lengthy constructions while maintaining a direct and effective style. This disciplined and laconic military style should be distinct from conventional literary norms. It should belong exclusively to military personnel individuals who speak little but convey much. Based on the framework of military education as articulated by Astafiev A.I., it follows that any military leader overseeing an organization must recognize that its effectiveness depends not only on internal factors (such as goals, objectives, personnel, and structure) but also on external influences (including politics, economics, state laws, and administration).

Astafiev A.I. was the first to substantiate that a military organization depends on the external environment and, in the modern sense, functions as an open system. P.A. Nikolaevich (1837–1900) confirmed several provisions on military management that remain relevant to this day [6]:

Military science establishes the general law that victory always favors those who can best integrate the conditions of force, time (timeliness), and place (terrain, space). These elements of victory possess the characteristics of a natural law and, therefore, remain unchanged.

Theory examines the properties of these elements as determined by science and analyzes their mutual influence in specific combinations to achieve a common result.

Creativity is entirely dependent on the personal qualities of a commander, his natural talent, and his abilities refined through knowledge and experience. Only the commander can determine when, where, and how to strike a decisive blow against the enemy and what methods to employ to ensure the enemy's complete defeat at a specific place and time, considering the given situation. Talent enables foresight and insight, allowing a commander to penetrate the enemy's secret intentions, anticipate challenges, and devise means to overcome them. Creativity in military strategy requires talent, experience, and scientific training.

Thus, Russian military theorists in the second stage made a significant contribution to the development of military management principles, ensuring effective troop control to accomplish assigned tasks.

By comparing the military management principles formulated by theorists in the second half of the 18th century with the principles developed by the founders of management schools in the first half of the 20th century, we can conclude that military theorists, through their works, were nearly 200 years ahead in formulating certain key management concepts.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the analysis conducted in this work, we present the following conclusions: Management is a process that involves planning, organizing, motivating, and controlling to establish and achieve an organization's goals through the efforts of others. The principle of management by objectives was first introduced in the second half of the 18th century. This marked a revolutionary shift in management thinking, as prior to that, managers primarily focused on functions and processes.

Drucker's idea that management should begin with goal development before shaping functions, interaction systems, and processes fundamentally changed the logic of management. The activities of a military organization are influenced by the external environment, meaning that a military organization operates as an open system. The recognition of the need to consider external influences in management emerged in the late 1950s. Since the principles of military management in the Suvorov school were formulated 50 to 200 years earlier than general management principles, it can be assumed that some aspects of Suvorov's military management were adopted by the founders of management schools.

The ancient Greek thinker Socrates made a significant contribution to the development of management science, particularly regarding the division of labor and specialization. He emphasized that management should ensure that each individual is in the right role, and he, along with other ancient Greek philosophers, argued that poverty in society often results from poor labor distribution.

Many principles of Russian military theorists reflect and expand upon the military management concepts of Suvorov A.V., making them followers of his school of thought. Military theorists of Russia, including Pestel, Medem, Milyutin, Goremykin, Astafyev, Dragomirov, and Petrov, can be regarded as the founders of the science, practice, and art of military management. It is also likely that some aspects of military management were later incorporated into general management theories.

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